

Citing preprints is wrong, apparently

Cite as: Coates, J.A., 2021. Citing preprints is wrong, apparently. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5789938

Do I even really need to write a whole thing about why it is ridiculously unacceptable to not cite previous work or code (unless that previous work has been retracted)?

The Tweet that prompted the post

Apparently, I do need to write a whole thing. The above is just the latest example of a semi-frequent argument I come across on Twitter. As you can see, most of the responses would limit the citation of preprints in some or all settings.

My slightly sarcastic response here is actually a valid point but let me take some time to make that point more seriously.

Science is built upon other science

When it comes to knowledge, we can't advance without appreciating and understanding where we've come from. That's fundamentally how science works—we incrementally build on previous research. To not acknowledge that previous work is well established as unacceptable behaviour—also it's outright plagiarism. However, this unacceptableness appears to depend on if that work has been peer-reviewed or not.

Peer review does NOT equal validation

Yet an alarming number of scientists and academics seem to be under the illusion that peer review does actually validate the work. There is an increasing amount of evidence looking into this (which I've covered briefly in an opinion piece [here](#)). The key takeaway—preprints are generally comparable to published versions. This is also reflected in surveys investigating the motivations behind posting preprints; most authors post a preprint because they believe that their work is ready to be shared.

[Opinion: The Rise of Preprints Is No Cause for Alarm](#)

[The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a cultural shift in the way that science is communicated and shared. Traditional...www.the-scientist.com](#)

But if you're still worried, preprints are citable—this means the work you cite is traceable and therefore, if it does change upon publication, that isn't your issue. The work you cited is cited correctly. In fact, work that does change may even be an important discussion point.

The freedom of choice

Access to knowledge is a fundamental human right; Article 27 of the Declaration on Human rights states “(1) *Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits*”. *Interpretations can differ but I would argue that the right to share in scientific advancement is infringed when those advances are hidden behind highly expensive paywalls. How does this relate to our discussion about not citing preprints? Well, if I hold this belief then why can't I choose to not cite articles based on where they are published (i.e. not citing articles from journals owned by for-profit publishers)?* I can't... Because that would be unacceptable and I'd be accused of plagiarism. This must work the other way around too, you can't choose to not cite a preprint because it is not in a peer-reviewed journal. That's you seeing and benefiting from the work of others and then outright plagiarising it.

Funders and journals mostly allow the citation of preprints

If the moral argument above hasn't convinced you, then perhaps a simpler one will. Most journals (and funders) allow the citation of preprints in manuscripts and grants. Just as it is unacceptable (though occurs) for reviewers to demand authors cite the reviewers own work, it should not be acceptable for a review to demand the removal of a citation because it is a preprint.

It is still important to know the individual rules of funders and journals (as the recent [disastrous decision by the Australian research council](#) (ARC) highlights). But as time goes by more and more funders and journals are adopting preprints

Ultimately, if you find yourself asking if you should cite a preprint or not instead try asking yourself if you're happy to plagiarise and how you'd feel if somebody took your ideas and work without appropriate credit.